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Towards Disruptive LCOE: Empirical Validation of a Surface-Piercing, Vertical-Axis, Variable-Pitch, Marine Hydro-Kinetic Turbine

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Abstract

A novel variable-pitch (VP), vertical-axis, surface-piercing, vertically actuated marine hydro-kinetic (MHK) turbine has been developed in partnership with Adaptide which offers an alternative to existing stall, speed, or independent pitch control approaches. This new MHK turbine architecture enables proactive debris avoidance, improved survival of infrequent extreme current speeds, reduced need for site characterization, increased capacity factor, and possible reduction of the levelized cost of energy (LCOE). The surface-piercing turbine may be vertically actuated automatically to remove the turbine blades from the flow during infrequent extreme conditions and/or avoid sensed debris. The VP turbine design was developed from a fixed pitch (FP) Adaptide prototype which demonstrated that a 20% power coefficient was achievable with a rudimentary design at reduced scale. The VP design shall operate at increased scale as compared to the FP design and utilizes an inexpensive mechanical pitching system. Low-cost benefits were maintained while increasing max C_p potential as compared to the FP design. Numerical studies were conducted to work towards an optimal pitch law with awareness of the literature, VP mechanism kinematics, and parasitic power losses.

Keywords: Variable-Pitch; MHK Turbine; Surface-Piercing

1. Problem Overview

Limiting factors which prevent widespread implementation of MHK turbines are shaft power modulation, costly site characterization requirements, low-capacity factor, and relatively expensive operation and maintenance costs.

Vertical actuation of a surface-piercing, vertical-axis turbine may enable renewable power generation from aggressive tidal and/or river resources which would destroy most or possibly all existing MHK devices. Additional benefits include proactive debris or fauna avoidance and significant reduction or elimination of the need for site characterization prior to deployment.

The Adaptide turbine may enable a disruptive reduction of the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) through maximization of capacity factor at a range of flow speeds and a simple, low-cost VP mechanism design. Partial submergence of the foils may further reduce long term costs by enabling maximal ease of access to all electrical and mechanical components which may require maintenance. Accordingly, the Adaptide turbine may be a viable alternative to fossil fuel-based power generation when implemented at scale.

2. Introduction

Adaptide recently tested a FP MHK turbine at reduced scale which illustrated the feasibility of viable efficiency with a rudimentary design. This study aims to improve the performance characteristics of the FP design with the introduction of a cam-follower pitching system. This novel system allows the foils to rotate about their own axes to achieve a desired angle between the chord line and the relative flow velocity, known as angle of attack (AOA). Coefficient of power (C_p), a measure of turbine performance, may then be significantly increased through an increased lift coefficient, a function of AOA [1, 2, 3]. Numerical and experimental studies in the literature utilize both active and passive pitching systems. Active pitching systems theoretically enable any pitching law; however, they are more complex and therefore could prove to be prohibitively expensive. The novel Adaptide device utilizes a passive VP mechanism, which is an application-specific cam-follower mechanism, to maintain a low associated cost increase while enabling a pitching law that is close to the optimal defined for an active pitch system.

3. Methodology

Per CFD results and prior VP work in the literature, and first-principles boundary calculations, a candidate pitching function has been developed. Refinement of this initial candidate law is in process. NACA 2412 foils were chosen to optimize performance in the low Reynold's number prototype regime; the foils enable maximal power generation in the upstream arc of blade travel ($0^\circ < \Theta < 180^\circ$) while accepting a lower maximum power generation limit in the downstream arc where the flow field is diminished. Initially, a conservative approach which will increase C_p relative to the FP device while minimizing potential for power loss in the downstream arc ($180^\circ < \Theta < 360^\circ$) of the turbine will be implemented [3]. Pitching laws will be embodied into the aforementioned cam-follower mechanism to impart the desired AOA adjustment – enabling a pitch law which is as near as possible to optimal. Per first-principles analysis, awareness of parasitic cam power losses and blade pitching accuracy is monitored throughout this process.

Initial empirical testing will be conducted with a cam that does not impart any pitch adjustment, operating as a FP turbine to determine the parasitic losses due to the VP mechanism. Quantifying the parasitic losses is central in ensuring the predicted performance benefits outweigh the power losses of the more complex system. Further testing will first implement a conservative pitching law, then increase to more complex pitching laws to demonstrate compelling turbine performance.

4. Discussion

Many of the empirical tests conducted in the literature are in highly controlled environments and neglect empirical effects such as flume blockage, surface chop, ventilation, and turbine to waterline clearance [4]. FP testing indicated that significant clearance between the upper spider supporting the foils and the air-water interface was essential to ensure consistent turbine performance and reduce parasitic drag. All testing shall be performed in a real-world environment which provides valuable insight and quantification of such effects.

Adaptide's design as a surface-piercing turbine has no submerged shaft, an architecture which has achieved efficiencies well beyond 35% in FP testing per the literature [5]. The use of a NACA 2412 asymmetrical foil was chosen to optimize performance in the forecasted low Reynold's number operational regime.

5. Conclusion

Vertical actuation of a surface-piercing, vertical-axis turbine may enable significant power generation in aggressive tidal and river flows and avoid debris which would destroy or significantly reduce the performance of existing MHK devices. In addition, there is no need for precise site characterization to install and operate the Adaptide turbine. Ultimately, these advantages may significantly reduce the associated LCOE of the Adaptide turbine and increase commercial viability of marine power generation.

In developing Adaptide's VP MHK turbine per the extensive literature, and in parallel with numerical models of optimal pitching laws and first-principles pitching mechanism analyses, it is expected that significant performance gains can be demonstrated relative to Adaptide's FP turbine. The development of a simple cam-follower system and associated near-optimal pitching law is anticipated to enable further reduction of LCOE.

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